

exostosin glycosyltransferase 1 (EXT1) : Machine learning discoveries of 2nd order synergy in Meningiomas

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Abstract

Background : Exostosin-1 is a protein that encoded by the EXT1 which is one of the two endoplasmic reticulum-resident type II transmembrane glycosyltransferase, that is involved in the chain elongation step of heparan sulfate biosynthesis. Mutations in this gene cause the type I form of multiple exostoses. It is also implicated in Langer-Giedion syndrome (tricho-rhino-phalangeal syndrome type II, TRPS II), hereditary multiple exostoses, osteochondromas, breast and prostate cancer, hypertrichosis, mental retardation, epilepsy, non- small cell lung carcinoma, gastric cancer, uterine corpus endometrial carcinoma, Sjögren's syndrome, Zika virus (ZIKV) infection and osteoarthritis, to name a few. However, its role in meningiomas has not yet been determined completely. Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 tumors from all 3 World Health Organization (WHO) grades (I through III) using clinical, gene expression, and sequencing data and using unsupervised clustering analysis identified 3 molecular types (A, B, and C) that reliably predicted recurrence. Further, these groups did not directly correlate with the WHO grading system, which classifies more than half of the tumors in the most aggressive molecular type as benign. **Issue** : Increasing evidence point to the fact that meningioma classification and grading, that is based on histopathology does not always accurately predict tumor aggressiveness and recurrence behaviour and knowledge of the underlying biology of the treatment resistant meningiomas and the impact of genetic alterations in these tumors, is lacking. At the current stage more genomic studies are required to unravel the role of other genes and their interations with other genetic factors. **Resolution** : In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. Adapting this search engine to the Meningioma dataset, i present here 2nd order combinations of EXT1, some of which have been known to exist via wet lab experiments, but many are yet to be tested. The reveals combinations might help oncologists/biologists test possible hypotheses that might be the causing factors in meningioma. Further, in my limited grasp, if proven true, the combinations revealed

^{*}ML dicoveries of EXT1 synergy in Meningiomas

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by the search engine might pave way for development of gene based therapies aimed at resolving pathological issues related to meningiomas.

Keywords: EXT1, Meningioma, Sensitivity analysis, Machine learning.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Meningioma

Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. They arise from the arachnoid cap cells. These arachnoid cap cells are specialized cells that make up the arachnoid mater (one of the three protective membranes covering the brain and spinal cord). The arachnoid mater is one of the three meninges. The other two that constitute the meninges are dura mater and pia mater.

1.1.1. World Health Organization (WHO) classification

The meningiomas are classified into three grades by WHO under the Central Nervous System tumours, namely, Grade I (benign), Grade II (atypical) and Grade III (anaplastic/malignant), based on histopathology or subtype (Louis et al. [3]). As of 2021, there exists 12 histopathological meningioma subtypes according to a mini-review by Torp

et al. [4]. They are meningothelial, fibrous, transitional, psammomatous, angioma-tous, microcystic, secretory, lymphoplasmacyte-rich, atypical, chordoid, clear cell and anaplastic (malignant) meningioma.

1.1.2. Historical perspective

Czarnetzki et al. [5] investigated a skull that was excavated at Steinheim/Murr (Baden-Wurttemberg, Germany) and consisted of a well preserved plagiocephalic cranium, with most of the facial skeleton intact. Their results of stratigraphical dating suggested the fossil specimen of *Homo steinheimensis*, was about 3,65,000 years old. In the fossile, they found that several features of the inner cranial table were consistent with a diagnosis of meningioma.

As documented in Okonkwo and Laws Jr [6], in 1614, Felix Plater, Professor of Medicine, issued a case report from the University of Basel on Caspar Bonecurtius, a noble knight stating -

began to lose his mind gradually over a two year period, to such an extent that finally he was completely stupefied and did nothing rationally. He had no desire for food and ate only when forcibly fed. ... Finally after matters had gone on thus for six months, he died.

Further, the autopsy report of Plater stated the following -

a round fleshy tumor, like an acorn. It was hard and full of holes and was as large as a medium-sized apple. It was covered with its own membrane and was entwined with veins. However, it was free of all connections with the matter of the brain, so much so that when it was removed by hand, it left behind a remarkable cavity.

This was the first case in the history that documented a patient with a lesion that was most compatible with a meningioma.

Next, in a contribution by Italian scientists, Paterniti [7] documents the first contribution of Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri in 1813 in a manuscript *Trattato di Chirurgia Pratica*, which was never published. Its discovery was made accidentally by David Giordano, who referred in detail in an article on surgeon of Pisa in *La chirurgia di Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri*. *Riv Storia Sci MedNat*. 1927: XVIII (3-4): 75-106. The unpublished manuscript of 488 pages describes that Vacca Berlinhieri proposed and performed a most bold radical operation. After a craniectomy with five or six burr holes on the outskirts of the fungus, the tumor was removed together the dura mater from which it originated, tying the cut vessels.

In 1847, Zanobi Pecchioli, Professor of Clinical Surgery and Operative Medicine at Modena and then at Siena University, published an account of surgeries performed during 16 years, from 1832 to 1847 (16 of the 1524 reported operations involved trephining of the skull). In one of these interventions, he carried out on July 29 1835, in Siena, for the resection of a meningioma, a defined fungus of the duramater. The case was not referred in the literature by Pecchioli but was described by in Pecchioli [8]. Finally, Cushing [9] coined the modern term of "meningioma".

Figure 1: A schematic diagram of different pathways in different meningiomas, as provided by Szulzewsky et al. [12] under CC-BY Attribution 4.0 International license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

1.1.3. Pathophysiology

Meningiomas arise from arachnoidal cap cells, most of which are near the vicinity of the venous sinuses, and this is the site of greatest prevalence for meningioma formation. The dural venous sinuses (also called dural/cerebral/cranial sinuses) are venous sinuses (channels) found between the periosteal and meningeal layers of dura mater in the brain. They receive blood from the cerebral veins, and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) from the subarachnoid space via arachnoid granulations. They mainly empty into the internal jugular vein. Cranial venous sinuses communicate with veins outside the skull through emissary veins. These communications help to keep the pressure of blood in the sinuses constant. (contributors [10] and Pamir et al. [11]) A schematic diagram for different pathways in different meningiomas has been provided in figure 1.

1.2. exostosin glycosyltransferase 1 (EXT1)

The **Langer-Giedion syndrome (tricho-rhino-phalangeal syndrome type II, TRPS II)** is characterized by craniofacial dysmorphism and skeletal abnormalities. It combines the clinical features of TRPS I and multiple cartilaginous exostoses (EXT). Lüdecke et al. [13] studied chromosome 8 deletions, translocations, an inversion, and an insertion in patients with TRPS I, TRPS II or EXT. Their results pointed to the fact that the TRPS gene maps more than 1,000 kb proximal to the EXT1 gene and that both genes were affected in TRPS II.

Hereditary multiple exostoses is an autosomal dominant disorder that is characterized by short stature and multiple, benign bone tumours. In a majority of families, the genetic defect in EXT1 is linked to the Langer-Giedion syndrome chromosomal region in 8q24.1. From this region, Ahn et al. [14] cloned and characterized a cDNA which spans chromosomal breakpoints previously identified in two multiple exostoses patients. Furthermore, they observed that the gene harboured frameshift mutations in affected members of two EXT1 families. However, recent studies in sporadic and exostosis-derived chondrosarcomas suggested that the 8q24.1-encoded EXT1 gene might have tumour suppressor function.

1.3. Roles of EXT1 in different disease

Osteochondromas occur as sporadic solitary lesions or as multiple lesions, characterizing the hereditary multiple exostoses syndrome (EXT). Approximately 15% of all chondrosarcomas arise within the cartilaginous cap of an osteochondroma. Bovée et al. [15] cloned two genes, EXT1 and EXT2, located on 8q24 and 11p11-p12, respectively and studied loss of heterozygosity and DNA ploidy in eight sporadic and six hereditary osteochondromas. EXT-1/2-mutation analysis was performed in a total of 34 sporadic and hereditary osteochondromas and secondary peripheral chondrosarcomas. Further, they demonstrated osteochondroma to be a true neoplasm, since aneuploidy was found in 4 of 10 osteochondromas. Moreover, LOH was almost exclusively found at the EXT1 locus in 5 of 14 osteochondromas and 4 novel constitutional cDNA alterations were detected in exon 1 of EXT1. They observed that 2 patients with multiple osteochondromas demonstrated a germline mutation combined with loss of the remaining wild-type allele in 3 osteochondromas, indicating that, in cartilaginous cells of the growth plate, inactivation of both copies of the EXT1 gene was required for osteochondroma formation in hereditary cases. In contrast, no somatic EXT1 cDNA alterations were found in sporadic osteochondromas.

Gain of chromosome arm 8q is a frequent genetic alteration in **breast and prostate cancer**. Two amplified subregions, 8q2s1 and 8q23-24, have been identified with comparative genomic hybridization (CGH). Nupponen et al. [16] mapped the amplified region around EIF3S3 in primary breast cancers and cell lines. On analyzing the expression of all expressed sequence tags (ESTs) located within and near this region, in addition to EIF3S3, they found that the 3 anonymous ESTs and EXT1 were highly expressed in cancer cell lines with the amplification at 8q23-q24. However, the anonymous ESTs were located outside the minimal highly amplified region and EXT1 was overexpressed only in one of the cancer cell lines with 8q amplification.

Wuyts et al. [17] described a boy with multiple exostoses, **hypertrichosis**, **mental retardation**, and **epilepsy** due to a de novo deletion on chromosome 8q24. Their molecular analysis revealed that the deletion interval overlapped with the Langer-Giedion syndrome and involved the EXT1 gene and additional genes located distal to EXT1, but probably not encompassing the TRPS1 gene located proximal to EXT1.

Kong et al. [18] screened prognostic DNA methylation sites and mRNAs in **non-small cell lung carcinoma** (NSCLC) data set from TCGA, and further validated using the samples retrospectively collected, and EXT1 was identified as a potential target. They found that gene body methylation of three CpG sites (cg03276982, cg11592677,

cg16286281) on EXT1 was significantly associated with clinical outcome, and the EXT1 gene expression also predicted prognosis. Further, knocking down of EXT1 resulted in decreased proliferation and migration. They also found that the Wnt signalling was the potential downstream target of EXT1 and their analyses revealed that the EXT1 targeted the β -catenin and effect migration rate of NSCLC cell lines. In conclusion, they showed that EXT1 methylation regulated the gene expression, effected the proliferation and migration via WNT pathway and predicted a poor prognosis for NSCLC.

Jiang et al. [19] elucidated the pivotal role of hsa_circ_0008035 (Circular RNAs, i.e circRNAs) in **gastric cancer** progression and immune evasion. Mechanistically, they found that hsa_circ_0008035 encoded the novel protein EXT1-219aa, suppressing EXT1 phosphorylation and expression. Additionally, they observed that hsa_circ_0008035 regulated pyruvate metabolism by influencing the nucleus localization of PKM2. The identified EXT1/PKM2 axis further underscored the intricate regulatory mechanisms orchestrated by hsa_circ_0008035 in gastric cancer.

Uterine corpus endometrial carcinoma (UCEC) is one of the most common gynecologic tumors. Chen et al. [20] performed Western blot and RT-qPCR to detect protein and mRNA expression of EXT1 in UCEC cell lines. EXT1 was identified as a potential target and its expression and methylation levels were both increased in UCEC tissues and cell lines, as well as elevated EXT1 was closely related to the poor prognosis of patients. Further, the knockdown of EXT1 significantly inhibited the malignant biological behaviors in UCEC cells. Additionally, their study also found that the deletion of 1559-2146 bp CpG island segment upregulated EXT1 expression and promoted malignant biological behaviors in UCEC cells. Also, they found the presence of m7G RNA methylation in UCEC cells. In conclusion, they observed that the methylation of EXT1 influenced the gene expression, thereby affecting the malignant biological behaviors in UCEC cells and regulating the pathological progression of UCEC.

Qiu et al. [21] investigated the spectrum and prognosis of membranous nephropathy (MN) in patients with **Sjögren's syndrome** (SS). For this, a total of 290 SS patients with kidney involvement were enrolled. Within the PLA2R-negative group, they found that 5 of 15 showed positivity for EXT1/EXT2 antigen and one out of eight for THSD7A antigen. They concluded that MN had become the predominant renal pathologic type in SS. PLA2R-positivity testing followed by EXT1/EXT2 and THSD7A testing was recommended for SS-MN patients.

Ling et al. [22] reported that exostosin glycosyltransferase 1 (EXT1), the heparan sulfate (HS) polymerase, was a critical regulatory factor for **Zika virus (ZIKV) infection**. Knocking out EXT1 dramatically restricted ZIKV infection, which is not due to the inhibition of virus entry resulting from HS deficiency, but mediated by the downregulation of autophagy. Further, they observed that induction of autophagy promoted ZIKV infection, and attenuated autophagy was found in distinct EXT1 knockout (EXT1-KO) cell lines. Over-expressing EXT1 resulted in the reduction of ZIKV production. The different roles of EXT1 in ZIKV infection were further confirmed by the data that knocking down EXT1 at the early stage of ZIKV infection repressed viral infection, whereas the increase of ZIKV infection was observed when knocking down EXT1 at the late stage of viral infection.

Osteoarthritis (OA) is a chronic joint disorder. Yuan et al. [23] explored one-pot-

synthesized gelatin microspheres devoid of glutaraldehyde as a novel biomaterial for OA management. Further, focusing on the Ext1 gene, critical for cartilage development and downregulated in OA, they investigated its restoration and immune regulation using gelatin microspheres cultured with mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs). They observed that OA patients exhibited decreased expression of the EXT1 gene in the medial compartment (lesion zone) cartilage area, accompanied by abnormal expression of immune regulatory genes. Culturing MSCs with the microspheres led to enhanced overexpression of the EXT1 gene, which is crucial for cartilage growth and development. Additionally, they found that microspheres regulated immune responses, contributing to a reduction in OA symptoms.

Many of the different synergies represented as combinations of genes/proteins have been experimentally tested and published. However, there are combinations that have yet to be explored. I address the problem of identifying these unexplored combinations via use of a machine learning based search engine in the next section.

1.4. Insight behind the work

Across all search engines has the fundamental principle remains the same i.e to capture the pattern available in the data and based on that pattern, rank a list of queries. Different algorithms can be applied, however if the fundamental pattern is captured accurately, then the rankings will remain approximately the same, with slight variations, across the different kinds of search engines used. I use one search engine, however, vary the way the patterns are captured via use of different sensitivity methods. Each sensitivity method uses a different flavour/mathematical formulation to compute the sensitivity indices to estimate the influence of the involved factors. These involved factors are genes that play a role in cell biology, in the above research. The insight is that all methods will capture the sensitivity of the involved factors based on their recorded regulations and the search engine will rank the combination of factors based on these sensitivity indices. Since the role of involved factors are captured properly, the search engine will give appropriate rankings to the combinations, thus capturing which gene combinations might be playing significantly in a biological phenomena. The above work shows rankings for experimentally confirmed combinations as well as unexplored/untested combinations. These rankings are not just numbers. They point to the existence of biological synergy in the form of gene combinations, whether tested in wet lab or unexplored till now. Finally, the findings suggest that the rankings are conserved across the different sensitivity methods used.

1.5. Combinatorial search problem and a possible solution

In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. The work uses SVM package by Joachims [24] in https://www.cs.cornell.edu/people/tj/svm_light/svm_rank.html. I use the adaptation to rank 2^{nd} order gene combinations. The sensitivity package by Pujol et al. [25] was used to develop the search engine pipeline. The current research uses the Hilbert Schmidt Independence

Criterion (HSIC) and SOBOL method, implemented in the sensitivity package mentioned above. I use three different kernels under the HSIC method namely, • laplace, • linear and • rbf. For SOBOL method, I use • sobol-2002, and • sobol-jansen. Each of these variants or kernels have been implemented in the sensitivity package and option has been provided in the search engine code to generate the rankings for a particular gene, using a choice of a kernel/variant at a time. Technical details about the variants and kernels can be found in references cited in Pujol et al. [25].

2. Methods

2.1. Static data from Patel et al. [1]

Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 meningioma samples from 140 patients, and according to the WHO histopathological classification system for meningioma, they found 121 tumors were of grade I (benign), 32 were of grade II (atypical), and 7 were of grade III (malignant). To determine whether meningiomas could be differentiated based on gene expression profiles, they used principal component analysis (PCA) on a discovery set of 97 tumors (i.e 77 WHO grade I and 20 WHO grade II). Next, they employed nonnegative matrix factorization (NMF) clustering (a unsupervised machine-learning approach) for $k = 2$ to $k = 7$ using the 1,500 genes that varied most among the tumor samples. They report that after 1,000 iterations, 3 clusters ($k = 3$) emerged as providing the best fit as determined by the consensus membership, cophenetic, and silhouette scores. They evaluated the cluster significance of the 3 subtypes using SigClust (Huang et al. [26]) and observed statistical significance between cluster boundaries, which exhibited significant differences in WHO grade representation.

2.2. Design for static data from Patel et al. [1]

The procedure begins with the listing of all C_k^n combinations for k number of genes from a total of n genes. Here n can be the choice of the biologist. k is ≥ 2 and $\leq (n - 1)$. Each of the combination of order k represent a unique set of interaction between the involved genetic factors. Since the sensitivity analysis methods require a sample for a particular observation, a steep gaussian distribution was generated with a jitter (noise) added to the deviation from the reported point measurement of 0.005. In this experiment, the distribution contained 10 measurements (including the point of measurement under consideration). This is repeated for each point of measurement.

To have an averaged ranking, the experiment was designed to run for 25 iterations. In each iteration, the datasets are combined in a specified format which go as input as per the requirement of a particular sensitivity analysis method. Thus for each p^{th} combination in C_k^n combinations, the dataset is prepared in a required format. Details of formatting the data have not been presented in the article to maintain the fluidity and brevity. Interested readers can find examples of forming the data in the sensitivity analysis package in R. Sensitivity analysis and its relevance in systems biology have been covered in a recently published article by Sinha [27], which forms the foundation for this work. After the data has been transformed, vectorized programming is

employed for density based sensitivity analysis and looping is employed for variance based sensitivity analysis to compute the required sensitivity indices for each of the p combinations.

After the above sensitivity indices have been stored for each of the p^{th} combination, for a chosen sensitivity analysis method, the next step in the design of experiment is conducted. Here, the indices are averaged per combination to have a mean index value. These index values form the discriminative features for a particular combination. For a k^{th} order combination, a vector of k elements or indices forms a feature vector. Thus for C_k^n combinations there will be C_k^n vectors, each containing k elements. Next, SVM_{learn}^{Rank} Joachims [24] is used to generate a model on default value C value of 20. In the current experiment on toy model C value has not been tuned. The training set helps in the generation of the model as the different gene combinations are numbered in order which are used as rank indices. The model is then used to generate score on the observations in the testing set using the $SVM_{classify}^{Rank}$ Joachims [24]. This is followed by sorting of these scores along with the rank indices already assigned to the gene combinations. The end result is a sorted order of the gene combinations based on the ranking score learned by the SVM^{Rank} algorithm.

Note that the following is the order in which the files should be executed in R Team [28], in order, for obtaining the desired results (Note that the code will not be explained here) - • use source("extractMeningiomadata.R") • use source("manuscript-2-2.R") • use source("SVMRank-Results-S-mean.R").

2.3. Translating the pipeline into code of execution in R

The execution begins by some preprocessing of the file containing the information regarding the down regulated genes via `source("extractMeningiomadata.R")`. The library containing the sensitivity analysis methods is then loaded in the interface using the command `library(sensitivity)` (Note - this package can be downloaded for free from <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/sensitivity/index.html>). Next a gaussian distribution for a particular transcript level for a gene is generated to have a sample. This is needed in the computation of sensitivity index for that particular gene. A gene of particular choice is selected (in blue) and the choice of the combination is made (here $k = 2$). Later a kernel is used (here rbf for HSIC method). 25 different indices are generated which help in generating aggregate rank using these 25 indices. The Support vector ranking algorithm is employed to generate the scores for different combinations and these scores are then sorted out. This is done using the command `source("SVMRank - Results - S - mean.R")`. A file is generated that contains the combinations in increasing order of influence. Note that 1 means lowest rank and vice versa, for 2^{nd} order combinations for any gene using a particular density based sensitivity index.

2.4. Regarding biological insight

For the recorded gene expression values, the sensitivity indices are computed. The search engine uses the kernel based density method. The kernel method takes the data, that is in a lower dimensional plane and projects it to a higher dimensional plane,

with an idea that in a higher dimensional place, there exists a dot product between the projected data. To simply state, the idea is that in a higher dimensional plane the nonlinearities between the data (in lower dimensional plane) will be captured and the data may be segregated from each other via a hyperplane. So, irrespective of the method used to measure the gene expression values, if the measurements capture biological information (to whatever extent they can), then the kernel method will be able to capture the nonlinearities/synergies, if existing and allow the sensitivity analysis method (here density based method) to estimate the strength of influence of each of the factors. Based on the sensitivity indices of combinations of a particular order, the search engine ranks the combinations. Details of search engine are provided in the published work in Sinha [2].

It is important to note that the search engine will not give insight about the mechanism of synergy between the components of a combination. However, if the synergy exists between components of an unexplored/untested combination, then the sensitivity indices will capture the influence of these components taken together (which form a combination of interest) and will rank the combination appropriately. These rankings provide insight about which combination a biologist/oncologist might want to test in a forest of combinations for a given scenario in a cell (whether normal or pathological).

3. Results & Discussion

3.1. EXT1 related synergies

Note - EXT1 was found to be upregulated in Type B. Upregulation was defined as Type logFC to be > 1 and FDR ≤ 0.001 , in Patel et al. [1]. Also, sorting of scores by the machine learning algorithm were done in ascending order, i.e - top is lowest in ranking. A total of 392 nd order combinations of EXT1 were recorded.

3.1.1. EXT1 - individual genes

The following genes in combination with EXT1 showed high rankings - CD38 molecule (CD38), C-C motif chemokine ligand 26 (CCL26), CD4 molecule (CD4), arachidonate 5-lipoxygenase (ALOX5), CD74 molecule (CD74), RUNX family transcription factor 3 (RUNX3), four and a half LIM domains 1 (FHL1), collagen type IX alpha 2 chain (COL9A2), collagen type XI alpha 1 chain (COL11A1), tetraspanin 32 (TSPAN32), protein disulfide isomerase family A member 5 (PDIA5), protein tyrosine phosphatase non-receptor type 3 (PTPN3), adenylate cyclase 2 (ADCY2), integrin subunit beta 5 (ITGB5), matrix metalloproteinase 2 (MMP2), solute carrier family 23 member 2 (SLC23A2), proprotein convertase subtilisin/kexin type 5 (PCSK5), DNA meiotic recombinase 1 (DMC1), nuclear factor of activated T cells 4 (NFATC4), CD40 molecule (CD40), regulating synaptic membrane exocytosis 4 (RIMS4), C-C motif chemokine ligand 22 (CCL22), platelet derived growth factor receptor like (PDGFRL), epoxide hydrolase 3 (EPHX3), procollagen C-endopeptidase enhancer (PCOLCE), endoglin (ENG), cholinergic receptor nicotinic epsilon subunit (CHRNE), contactin associated protein 1 (CNTNAP1), peripheral myelin protein 22 (PMP22), tripartite motif contain-

ing 2 (TRIM2), collagen type XII alpha 1 chain (COL12A1), SAM and SH3 domain containing 1 (SASH1), vanin 1 (VNN1), solute carrier family 29 member 1 (Augustine blood group) (SLC29A1), growth hormone receptor (GHR), par-3 family cell polarity regulator beta (PARD3B), Wnt ligand secretion mediator (WLS), neuropilin 2 (NRP2), chromosome 1 open reading frame 198 (C1orf198), plexin domain containing 2 (PLXDC2), PDZ and LIM domain 2 (PDLIM2), cysteine rich secretory protein LCCL domain containing 1 (CRISPLD1), PHD finger protein 24 (PHF24), plasminogen activator, urokinase (PLAU), hematopoietic cell signal transducer (HCST), transmembrane protein 35A (TMEM35A), FCH and mu domain containing endocytic adaptor 1 (FCHO1), leukocyte immunoglobulin like receptor B2 (LILRB2), complement C1q like 1 (C1QL1), myosin heavy chain 10 (MYH10), leucine rich repeats and calponin homology domain containing 1 (LRCH1), lymphocyte cytosolic protein 1 (LCP1), alpha kinase 3 (ALPK3), ectonucleotide pyrophosphatase/phosphodiesterase 2 (ENPP2), interleukin 11 receptor subunit alpha (IL11RA), elastin microfibril interfacer 1 (EMILIN1), shroom family member 3 (SHROOM3), cerebellin 3 precursor (CBLN3), proline-serine-threonine phosphatase interacting protein 1 (PSTPIP1), insulin like growth factor binding protein 4 (IGFBP4), NLR family pyrin domain containing 12 (NLRP12), chromosome 1 open reading frame 162 (C1orf162), RNA binding motif single stranded interacting protein 3 (RBMS3), oxysterol binding protein like 10 (OSBPL10), CTD small phosphatase like (CTDSPL), family with sequence similarity 105 member A (FAM105A), tripartite motif containing 7 (TRIM7), solute carrier family 2 (facilitated glucose transporter), member 12 (SLC2A12), LanC like family member 3 (LANCL3), teneurin transmembrane protein 4 (TENM4), AT-rich interaction domain 5B (ARID5B), serine protease 23 (PRSS23), cysteine rich transmembrane BMP regulator 1 (CRIM1), potassium voltage-gated channel subfamily E regulatory subunit 4 (KCNE4), dimethylarginine dimethylaminohydrolase 1 (DDAH1), roundabout guidance receptor 3 (ROBO3), sushi domain containing 3 (SUSD3), myosin IE (MYO1E), SLAM family member 8 (SLAMF8), RUNX family transcription factor 1 (RUNX1), meiosis 1 associated protein (MIAP), trichohyalin (TCHH), coiled-coil-helix-coiled-coil-helix domain containing 6 (CHCHD6), sialic acid binding Ig like lectin 11 (SIGLEC11), sialic acid binding Ig like lectin 16 (gene/pseudogene) (SIGLEC16), LDL receptor related protein 5 (LRP5), matrix remodeling associated 8 (MXRA8), coiled-coil domain containing 74A (CCDC74A), amyloid beta precursor protein binding family B member 2 (APBB2), transmembrane protein 200A (TMEM200A), collagen type I alpha 2 chain (COL1A2), transmembrane protein 71 (TMEM71), HtrA serine peptidase 1 (HTRA1), trans-golgi network vesicle protein 23 homolog A (TVP23A), lactate dehydrogenase D (LDHD), 5'-nucleotidase domain containing 2 (NT5DC2), nephronectin (NPNT), atonal bHLH transcription factor 8 (ATOH8), coiled-coil domain containing 126 (CCDC126), G protein-coupled receptor 183 (GPR183), mono-ADP ribosylhydrolase 2 (MACROD2), pseudopodium enriched atypical kinase 1 (PEAK1), heart development protein with EGF like domains 1 (HEG1), yippee like 2 (YPEL2), family with sequence similarity 131 member A (FAM131A), BCL2 family apoptosis regulator BOK (BOK), MEF2 activating motif and SAP domain containing transcriptional regulator (MAMSTR), frizzled class receptor 8 (FZD8), phosphodiesterase 4D interacting protein (PDE4DIP), cysteine and serine rich nuclear protein 3 (CSRNP3), potassium voltage-gated channel subfamily E regulatory subunit 1 (KCNE1), PLAG1

zinc finger (PLAG1), EPH receptor B3 (EPHB3), phospholipase C beta 1 (PLCB1), neurotrimin (NTM), regulator of G protein signaling 6 (RGS6), pappalysin 1 (PAPPA), pyrroline-5-carboxylate reductase 1 (PYCR1), nebulin (NEB), transmembrane protein 119 (TMEM119), olfactomedin like 1 (OLFML1), dual specificity phosphatase 5 pseudogene 1 (DUSP5P1), adrenoceptor alpha 2C (ADRA2C), protein kinase D1 (PRKD1), colony stimulating factor 1 (CSF1), fibronectin leucine rich transmembrane protein 2 (FLRT2), protein kinase cGMP-dependent 1 (PRKG1), SHC adaptor protein 4 (SHC4), ankyrin repeat domain 20 family member A5, pseudogene (ANKRD20A5P), reticulon 4 receptor like 2 (RTN4RL2), A-kinase anchoring protein 19 (C2orf88 / AKAP19), kelch repeat and BTB domain containing 12 (KBTBD12), low density lipoprotein receptor class A domain containing 2 (LDLRAD2), placenta associated 9 (PLAC9), nuclear GTPase, germinal center associated (NUGGC), family with sequence similarity 180 member A (FAM180A), serine/threonine kinase 31 (STK31), membrane metalloendopeptidase (MME), family with sequence similarity 180 member B (FAM180B), dishevelled binding antagonist of beta catenin 3 (DACT3), C-type lectin domain containing 9A (CLEC9A), metallothionein 1F (MT1F), integrin subunit beta like 1 (ITGBL1), matrix metalloproteinase 17 (MMP17), zinc finger protein 521 (ZNF521), ryanodine receptor 3 (RYR3), dual specificity phosphatase and pro isomerase domain containing 1 (DUSP27), ras homolog family member T1 pseudogene 2 (RHOT1P2), phospholipid phosphatase 4 (PLPP4), family with sequence similarity 155 member A (FAM155A / NALF1), vitrin (VIT), ankyrin repeat domain 20 family member A9, pseudogene (ANKRD20A9P), glutathione peroxidase 3 (GPX3), high mobility group box 3 pseudogene 7 (HMGB3P7), ankyrin repeat domain 20 family member A11, pseudogene (ANKRD20A11P), teneurin transmembrane protein 3 (TENM3), RFPL1 antisense RNA 1 (RFPL1S), ITGB2 antisense RNA 1 (ITGB2-AS1), LMCD1 antisense RNA 1 (LMCD1-AS1), cytochrome P450 family 4 subfamily F member 29, pseudogene (CYP4F29P) and sorting nexin 18 pseudogene 13 (SNX18P13).

Using the adaptation of the above mentioned search engine, I tabulate the rankings of 2nd order combination of EXT1 with the above list, that were reported to be upregulated in Patel et al. [1]. Table 1 and 2 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 3 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 1 and 2.

One can also interpret the results of the table 1 and 2 graphically, with the following influences - • Individual members w.r.t EXT1 with EXT1 – > CD38 / CCL26 / CD4 / ALOX5 / CD74 / RUNX3 / FHL1 / COL9A2 / COL11A1 / TSPAN32 / PDIA5 / PTPN3 / ADCY2 / ITGB5 / MMP2 / SLC23A2 / PCSK5 / DMC1 / NFATC4 / CD40 / RIMS4 / CCL22 / PDGFRL / EPHX3 / PCOLCE / ENG / CHRNE / CNTNAP1 / PMP22 / TRIM2 / COL12A1 / SASH1 / VNN1 / SLC29A1 / GHR / PARD3B / WLS / NRP2 / C1orf198 / PLXDC2 / PDLIM2 / CRISPLD1 / PHF24 / PLAU / HCST / TMEM35A / FCHO1 / LILRB2 / C1QL1 / MYH10 / LRCH1 / LCP1 / ALPK3 / ENPP2 / IL11RA / EMILIN1 / SHROOM3 / CBLN3 / PSTPIP1 / IGFBP4 / NLRP12 / C1orf162 / RBMS3 / OSBPL10 / CTDSPL / FAM105A / TRIM7 / SLC2A12 / LANCL3 / TENM4 / ARID5B / PRSS23 / CRIM1 / KCNE4 / DDAH1 / ROBO3 / SUSP3 / MYO1E / SLAMF8 / RUNX1 / M1AP / TCHH / CHCHD6 / SIGLEC11 / SIGLEC16 / LRP5 / MXRA8 / CCDC74A / APBB2 / TMEM200A / COL1A2 / TMEM71 / HTRA1 / TVP23A / LDHD / NT5DC2 / NPNT / ATOH8 / CCDC126 /

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS EXT1									
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T EXT1									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
CD38 - EXT1	235	296	176	287	CCL26 - EXT1	219	305	133	260
CD4 - EXT1	318	278	294	19	ALOX5 - EXT1	211	297	303	347
CD74 - EXT1	239	156	224	391	RUNX3 - EXT1	309	250	182	342
FHL1 - EXT1	254	238	340	272	COL9A2 - EXT1	257	300	228	45
COL11A1 - EXT1	238	121	322	324	TSPAN32 - EXT1	271	259	378	312
PDIA5 - EXT1	259	354	304	4	PTPN3 - EXT1	246	204	230	265
ADCY2 - EXT1	63	286	338	316	ITGB5 - EXT1	289	379	293	221
MMP2 - EXT1	255	228	282	356	SLC23A2 - EXT1	256	376	236	32
PCSK5 - EXT1	251	222	327	251	DMC1 - EXT1	215	211	306	46
NFATC4 - EXT1	274	284	200	384	CD40 - EXT1	302	207	350	361
RIMS4 - EXT1	301	321	192	301	CCL22 - EXT1	229	108	271	271
PDGFRL - EXT1	140	294	297	306	EPHX3 - EXT1	209	146	278	266
PCOLCE - EXT1	306	362	346	339	ENG - EXT1	279	242	58	300
CHRNE - EXT1	205	256	187	307	CNTNAP1 - EXT1	290	270	137	370
PMP22 - EXT1	170	246	219	366	TRIM2 - EXT1	308	209	287	10
COL12A1 - EXT1	222	30	323	220	SASH1 - EXT1	272	180	345	344
VNN1 - EXT1	218	367	374	8	SLC29A1 - EXT1	184	213	291	208
GHR - EXT1	316	266	70	325	PARD3B - EXT1	304	271	296	322
WLS - EXT1	262	268	351	37	NRP2 - EXT1	202	318	344	290
C1orf198 - EXT1	264	372	264	317	PLXDC2 - EXT1	276	343	325	54
PDLIM2 - EXT1	230	252	384	336	CRISPLD1 - EXT1	333	251	329	372
PHF24 - EXT1	224	261	321	358	PLAU - EXT1	174	237	343	357
HCST - EXT1	315	153	261	373	TMEM35A - EXT1	231	288	234	43
FCHO1 - EXT1	151	308	299	385	LILRB2 - EXT1	299	68	270	383
C1QL1 - EXT1	268	208	210	283	MYH10 - EXT1	216	346	347	328
LRCH1 - EXT1	314	311	273	1	LCPI - EXT1	258	325	389	363
ALPK3 - EXT1	252	280	266	364	ENPP2 - EXT1	236	336	226	309
IL11RA - EXT1	317	352	379	23	EMILIN1 - EXT1	295	176	205	232
SHROOM3 - EXT1	143	241	305	279	CBLN3 - EXT1	129	302	365	227
PSTPIP1 - EXT1	107	245	214	319	IGFBP4 - EXT1	311	359	310	18
NLRP12 - EXT1	287	255	370	335	C1orf162 - EXT1	298	335	286	345
RBMS3 - EXT1	171	338	237	371	OSBPL10 - EXT1	192	267	212	297
CTDSP1 - EXT1	292	224	119	365	FAM105A - EXT1	232	226	300	44
TRIM7 - EXT1	190	273	223	248	SLC2A12 - EXT1	281	200	41	253
LANCL3 - EXT1	269	240	213	280	TENM4 - EXT1	150	287	279	229
ARID5B - EXT1	297	355	244	33	PRSS23 - EXT1	285	182	339	331
CRIM1 - EXT1	328	356	284	355	KCNE4 - EXT1	278	323	142	341
DDAH1 - EXT1	270	375	364	292	ROBO3 - EXT1	260	233	366	29
SUSD3 - EXT1	198	230	220	327	MYO1E - EXT1	156	307	254	302
SLAMF8 - EXT1	242	316	143	295	RUNX1 - EXT1	334	253	361	303

Table 1: 2nd order interaction ranking between EXT1 VS Individual members.

GPR183 / MACROD2 / PEAK1 / HEG1 / YPEL2 / FAM131A / BOK / MAMSTR / FZD8 / PDE4DIP / CSRN3 / KCNE1 / PLAG1 / EPHB3 / PLCB1 / NTM / RGS6 / PAPP / PYCR1 / NEB / TMEM119 / OLFML1 / DUSP5P1 / ADRA2C / PRKD1 / CSF1 / FLRT2 / PRKG1 / SHC4 / ANKRD20A5P / RTN4RL2 / C2orf88 / KBTBD12 / LDLRAD2 / PLAC9 / NUGGC / STK31 / MME / FAM180B / DACT3 / CLEC9A / MT1F / ITGBL1 / MMP17 / ZNF521 / RYR3 / DUSP27 / RHOT1P2 / PLPP4 / FAM155A / VIT / ANKRD20A9P / GPX3 / HMGB3P7 / ANKRD20A11P / TENM3 / RFPL1S / ITGB2-AS1 / LMCD1-AS1 / CYP4F29P / SNX18P13.

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS EXT1									
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T EXT1									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
MIAP - EXT1	296	304	375	63	TCHH - EXT1	253	281	373	30
CHCHD6 - EXT1	176	248	317	380	SIGLEC11 - EXT1	273	353	363	39
SIGLEC16 - EXT1	223	269	336	367	LRP5 - EXT1	87	361	381	348
MXRA8 - EXT1	227	295	232	49	CCDC74A - EXT1	286	272	334	40
APBB2 - EXT1	240	289	87	285	TMEM200A - EXT1	203	350	311	7
COL1A2 - EXT1	282	314	285	298	TMEM71 - EXT1	263	264	376	250
HTRA1 - EXT1	86	337	203	333	TVP23A - EXT1	157	340	201	386
LDHD - EXT1	221	303	349	392	NT5DC2 - EXT1	208	326	250	349
NPNT - EXT1	241	299	245	343	ATOH8 - EXT1	197	317	388	262
CCDC126 - EXT1	288	365	298	389	GPR183 - EXT1	319	277	269	36
MACROD2 - EXT1	161	232	307	352	PEAK1 - EXT1	280	347	274	3
HEG1 - EXT1	305	282	318	376	YPEL2 - EXT1	265	309	342	191
FAM131A - EXT1	226	138	290	350	BOK - EXT1	261	301	217	277
MAMSTR - EXT1	237	218	123	268	FZD8 - EXT1	210	329	263	310
PDE4DIP - EXT1	283	333	367	377	CSRNP3 - EXT1	201	327	356	5
KCNE1 - EXT1	132	276	283	216	PLAG1 - EXT1	307	349	314	308
EPHB3 - EXT1	341	348	96	374	PLCB1 - EXT1	388	320	295	200
NTM - EXT1	387	390	309	132	RGS6 - EXT1	357	358	319	112
PAPPA - EXT1	384	383	313	193	PYCR1 - EXT1	352	219	73	390
NEB - EXT1	344	249	207	323	TMEM119 - EXT1	353	369	235	202
OLFML1 - EXT1	383	368	308	82	DUSP5P1 - EXT1	361	357	324	270
ADRA2C - EXT1	340	225	372	182	PRKD1 - EXT1	390	334	260	89
CSF1 - EXT1	346	206	56	314	FLRT2 - EXT1	338	364	341	47
PRKG1 - EXT1	303	313	114	264	SHC4 - EXT1	370	234	288	187
ANKRD20A5P - EXT1	380	332	392	99	RTN4RL2 - EXT1	291	229	131	381
C2orf88 - EXT1	347	221	320	346	KBTBD12 - EXT1	332	324	218	281
LDLRAD2 - EXT1	391	374	251	106	PLAC9 - EXT1	363	371	380	79
NUGGC - EXT1	385	387	326	154	STK31 - EXT1	350	263	170	387
MME - EXT1	364	381	358	100	FAM180B - EXT1	389	388	292	125
DACT3 - EXT1	250	169	262	375	CLEC9A - EXT1	354	391	86	263
MT1F - EXT1	320	265	277	38	ITGBL1 - EXT1	330	290	67	362
MMP17 - EXT1	359	366	357	188	ZNF521 - EXT1	371	382	337	189
RYR3 - EXT1	372	344	102	239	DUSP27 - EXT1	331	279	229	338
RHOTIP2 - EXT1	374	363	258	180	PLPP4 - EXT1	349	339	377	234
FAM155A - EXT1	336	380	383	245	VIT - EXT1	365	384	385	134
ANKRD20A9P - EXT1	366	351	391	173	GPX3 - EXT1	378	342	289	88
HMGB3P7 - EXT1	369	331	368	146	ANKRD20A11P - EXT1	373	386	257	130
TENM3 - EXT1	386	377	386	110	RFPL1S - EXT1	367	117	242	388
ITGB2-AS1 - EXT1	337	378	359	224	LMCD1-AS1 - EXT1	324	215	206	304
CYP4F29P - EXT1	392	392	312	198	SNX18P13 - EXT1	335	373	382	197

Table 2: 2nd order interaction ranking between EXT1 VS Individual members.

4. Conclusion

Presented here are a range of multiple synergistic EXT1 2nd order combinations that were ranked via a machine learning based search engine. Via majority voting across the ranking methods it was possible to find plausible unexplored synergistic combinations of EXT1-X that might be prevalent in meningioma.

Conflict of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

Individual members w.r.t EXT1

CD38 / CCL26 / CD4 / ALOX5 / CD74 / RUNX3 ...
 FHL1 / COL9A2 / COL11A1 / TSPAN32 / PDIA5 ...
 PTPN3 / ADCY2 / ITGB5 / MMP2 / SLC23A2 ...
 PCSK5 / DMC1 / NFATC4 / CD40 / RIMS4 ...
 CCL22 / PDGFRL / EPHX3 / PCOLCE / ENG ...
 CHRNE / CNTNAP1 / PMP22 / TRIM2 / COL12A1 ...
 SASH1 / VNN1 / SLC29A1 / GHR / PARD3B ...
 WLS / NRP2 / C1orf198 / PLXDC2 / PDLIM2 ...
 CRISPLD1 / PHF24 / PLAUI / HCST / TMEM35A ...
 FCHO1 / LILRB2 / C1QL1 / MYH10 / LRCH1 ...
 LCP1 / ALPK3 / ENPP2 / IL11RA / EMILIN1 ...
 SHROOM3 / CBLN3 / PSTPIP1 / IGFBP4 / NLRP12 ...
 C1orf162 / RBMS3 / OSBPL10 / CTDSPL / FAM105A ...
 TRIM7 / SLC2A12 / LANCL3 / TENM4 / ARID5B ...
 PRSS23 / CRIM1 / KCNE4 / DDAH1 / ROBO3 ...
 SUSP3 / MYO1E / SLAMF8 / RUNX1 / M1AP / TCHH ...
 CHCHD6 / SIGLEC11 / SIGLEC16 / LRP5 / MXRA8 ...
 CCDC74A / APBB2 / TMEM200A / COL1A2 / TMEM71 ...
 HTRA1 / TVP23A / LDHD / NT5DC2 / NPNT / ATOH8 ...
 CCDC126 / GPR183 / MACROD2 / PEAK1 / HEG1 ...
 YPEL2 / FAM131A / BOK / MAMSTR / FZD8 / PDE4DIP ...
 CSRNP3 / KCNE1 / PLAG1 / EPHB3 / PLCB1 / NTM ...
 RGS6 / PAPP / PYCR1 / NEB / TMEM119 / OLFML1 ...
 DUSP5P1 / ADRA2C / PRKD1 / CSF1 / FLRT2 / PRKG1 ...
 SHC4 / ANKRD20A5P / RTN4RL2 / C2orf88 / KBTBD12 ...
 LDLRAD2 / PLAC9 / NUGGC / STK31 / MME / FAM180B ...
 DACT3 / CLEC9A / MT1F / ITGBL1 / MMP17 / ZNF521 ...
 RYR3 / DUSP27 / RHOT1P2 / PLPP4 / FAM155A / VIT ...
 ANKRD20A9P / GPX3 / HMGB3P7 / ANKRD20A11P / TENM3 ...
 RFPL1S / ITGB2-AS1 / LMCD1-AS1 / CYP4F29P / SNX18P13 EXT1

Table 3: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between EXT1 and Individual members.

Author's contributions

Concept, design, in silico implementation - SS. Analysis and interpretation of results -
 SS. Manuscript writing - SS. Manuscript revision - SS. Approval of manuscript - SS

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Source of Data

Data used in this research work was released in a publication in Patel et al. [1]. Permission to use, granted by PNAS.

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